

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING PROPER NOUNS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article covers the role of culture in presence and formation of proper nouns. The article deals with linguacultural peculiarities and translation problems of proper nouns. The linguacultural analysis of proper nouns demonstrates the relation of language with the history, spirituality and certainly, culture of nation. Taking into account of above mentioned features, the problems of translation of proper nouns from one language into another was mentioned in this article.

Key words: language, culture, proper nouns, identification, linguoculture, linguistic units, transcription, transliteration, semantic modification, description, tracing and commenting.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada atoqli otlarning paydo bo'lishi va shakllanishida madaniyatning o'rni, ularning lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari hamda tarjima muammolari xususida so'z yuritiladi. Atoqli otlarning linvomadaniy tahlili orqali tilning millat tarixi, ma'naviyati va albatta, madaniyati bilan o'zaro aloqasi namoyon bo'ladi. Ushbu munosabatlarni hisobga olgan holda, maqolada atoqli otlarni bir tildan ikkinchi tilga tarjima qilishdagi muammolar haqidagi fikrlar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: til, madaniyat, atoqli otlar, indentifikatsiya, lingvomadaniyat, til birliklari, transkripsiya, transliteratsiya, semantik modifikatsiya, tasvirlash, kalkalash va sharhlash.

Аннотация: Автор описывает значение культуры в возникновении и формировании имен собственных. В статье рассматриваются лингвокультурные особенности и проблемы перевода имен собственных. Лингвокультурный анализ имен собственных демонстрирует связь языка с историей, духовностью и, конечно, культуру нации. Исходя из вышеупомянутых особенностей, в статье изложены проблемы перевода имен собственных с одного языка на другой.

Ключевые слова: язык, культура, имена собственные, идентификация, лингвокультурология, языковые единицы, транскрипция, транслитерация, семантическая модификация, описание, калькирование и комментарий.

Recently, the problem of language and cultural harmony is gaining the attention of scientists, linguists and researchers. Different approaches to this topic of linguistics are done in the field of linguistic and cultural studies, psycholinguistics, ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics, history, literary studies, translation studies. Issues of language and culture balance conducted by scientists are highlighted in research works, their interdependent permanent units or complements are proven by them. It has been fully proven that they are important components. In the language, cultural values are expressed and delivered to the people, in this way language serves as the main tool.

Language is the landscape of the world, embodies the identity and national culture of the people. Interaction between language and culture, especially foreign language teaching is evident in the process. A person while learning his mother tongue gradually assimilates its national culture, traditions and perceives customs. But it is different in learning a foreign language perfectly, because people begin to understand the worldly view of the people and other nations. Today, one of the main goals of language teaching is to form communicative language skills in the learner

and their enrichment of the socio-cultural outlook, and to increase cultural level of opinions expressed in dialogues. Relationship between culture and language is one part of the complex psycholinguistic processes and in this process, translation is an important profession .

Translation is conveying the original meaning of information in linguistics. The goal is to find the appropriate units and use them effectively. It prioritizes interaction between foreign language culture and our own culture related to attitudes and individual differences and understanding of the world certain cognitive processes. In the combination of language and culture, as well as in the process of translation a person involuntarily come across nouns, which forms the important lexical structure of the language. Every nation and every different ethnic group in any period have their own onomastic units, namely, they will have a list of proper nouns. Proper nouns are important in demonstrating concepts in certain cultures. However, in many cases, it falls outside the focus of attention of learners and translators and researchers who deliver them in foreign and native language in the formation of proper nouns in oral speech. Particularly, ,lack of manuals, textbooks, dictionaries increases weightiness of the matter.

Famous linguist and translator D.I. Ermolovich's states, "Nouns are characterized with the knowledge that people need in the process of transition in formal, meaningful, and associative features, and overcoming barriers between languages and cultures "(3).Proper nouns, unlike common nouns, are characterized by the feature of obtaining universally use. They, in turn, express universal aspects of humans' thinking and the need to name himself. Naming a single entity is one of the basic speed, acts, included by the class of declaratives, alongside declaring war, dismissing and be questing. People and peaces, pets and hurricanes, and festivities, institution and commercial products, works of art and shops are given a name. Naming serves to highlight entities that play a role in people's daily life, and to establish and maintain an individually in a society.

Proper nouns (also called proper nouns) are the words which name specific people, organizations or places. They always start with a capital letter.

- Each part of a person's name is a proper noun – Lynne Hand, Elizabeth Helen, Ruth Jones.
- The names of companies, organizations or trade marks: - Microsoft, Rolls Royce, the Round Table, www.
- Given or pet names of animals – Lassie Triger Sam.
- The names of cities and countries and words derived from those proper nouns – Paris, London, New York, England.
- English Geographical and Celestial Names – The Red Sea, Alpha Centauri, Mars.
- Monuments, buildings, meeting rooms –The Taj Mahal, The Eiffel Tower, Room 222.
- Historical events, documents, law, and periods – The Civil War, the Industrial Revolution, World War 1.
- Month, days of week, holidays – Monday, Christmas, December.
- Religions, deities, scriptures – God, Christ, Jehovah, Christianity, Judaism, Islam, the Bible, the Torah, the Koran.
- Awards, vehicles, vehicle models and names – The Nobel Peace Prize, the Scout Movement, Ford Focus, the Bismarck

Along with cultural dominants, proper nouns are a national symbol of enlightenment and spirituality, and humanity itself in society special place and formation, its direct and inseparable connection with society, also describes the influence of society on human life. The translation of common nouns from one language to another is somewhat different complex and multifaceted process. The reason is that proper nouns as a carrier of information about the nation's national culture have properties, including that they have a second figurative meaning can be. In addition, the specific semantics of nouns structures determine the complexity of the translation process. The problem of translation of proper nouns is studied with the following aspects : firstly, from the point of view of their referentiality, secondly,

their connection with nominative and connotative aspects , thirdly, in terms of intercultural communication.

T.A. Kazakova separate lexical methods of translation of proper nouns emphasizes. The main function of proper nouns is individuals identification, they perform their task in the translation process along with are comparative autonomies that do not depend on the context participates. Proper nouns are important because they are translations to be able to reinforce the text being made in different directions has the ability. How to translate them into a foreign language depends on the translator's choice. These are two of the proper nouns bias feature, to them as non-standard language units specifies the approach. In such cases, translation from an interpreter There is a need to create special translation methods in the target language will be done. Basically, translation, transcription, transliteration, semantics a wide range of ways to modify, describe, copy and interpret is used.

Today, most of the proper nouns are in a second foreign languag translation with the help of graphic means, that is, with the method of transcription is being done. Transcription preserves the tone of pronunciation of words in the same language the rest is a method of translation into a second language. Transcription the inevitable difficulty is that one of the range of phonemes available in different languages is determined by not matching one. A method of transcription must distinguish not only translation on the one side but also transliteration on the other side. Common to transcription, translation and transliteration aspect, their acquisition of words from a certain language It is manifested in the fact that the language serves as a means of delivery. The difference lies in the tools used in this translation process is expressed.

Transcriptional translation of English proper nouns to do, causing a number of complications related to simple aspects emits First, in the transcription of common nouns in English the existing phoneme series does not exist in Uzbek. For example, the letter "th". phonemes [th] and [ð] of the combination (For example, Elizabeth [ə'lızə'be:th] – Elizabeta), in addition, a line that is opposed to each other and short

vowels do not exist in Uzbek, the phoneme [æ] (For example, Westminster Abbey [ˈæbi] – Westminster Abbey) is also in Uzbek does not occur. Second, of Old English orthography development caused a significant change in pronunciation. Pronounced and unpronounced letter and letter in words increased cases of compounds were observed.

Most of the proper nouns entered the Uzbek language many years ago entered, they are mainly historical, religious, folklore, mythological and artistic consists of names and titles related to literature. But transcribing in the process, all of them are read according to modern language standards and is written. The following groups of proper nouns are transcription and are translated using transliteration methods: anthroponyms (human names), abbreviated names, nicknames, surnames, toponyms, astronoms, choronyms, ethnonyms, musical instruments names, animal nicknames, organizations, institutions, books, names of movies, magazines, spaceships, firms, companies and others. Transcription and to them at the same time when transliteration methods are used in addition, it is necessary to use other translation methods will come Examples of these are semantic and mapping methods. For example, Amir Temur - in the form of Amir Temur, Temurlane, Temur the Great can be given. Translation of proper nouns among language units Another common method is ironing. In it, not sounds, but words or structural combinator of word combinations are restored. Parts of words (morphemes) or Phrases (lexemes) are the corresponding language in the target language is translated with elements. Most of the vocabulary in the political, scientific and cultural spheres part is translated by calking method. For example,

Mamlakat rahbari – Head of the government.

Oliy sud – Supreme Court.

Boshvazir – Prime Minister

If the geographical names of mountains, seas, lakes and other places in nature contain translatable components, they are also translated by calque:

Orange River – Sariq daryo

White Sea – Oq dengiz

Rocky mountains – Qoyali tog'lar, Roki tog'lari

South China Sea – Janubiy Xitoy dengizi

Copying, transliteration of the translation of proper nouns, Transcription or mixed methods are usually given in dictionaries. But, in most cases, especially historical-cultural names, rare geographical names that occur, translation in the translation of new terms The selection of the method is the responsibility of the translator and is independent of him a decision is required.

In inter-linguistic and inter-cultural relations and even nations The problem of translation of proper nouns in interactions between has retained its relevance despite being researched. The difficulty and shortcomings of the translation of proper nouns are also subjective (the translator has excellent knowledge of the language and general cultural knowledge to be) and objective (formation of nouns in language and oral speech characteristics) related to causes. Proper nouns from one language to another finding a solution to the problems that arise in the translation into the language requires high skill from the translator. This, in turn, languages and ensuring effective and successful intercultural relations serves to give.

Chulpon in his translation takes the appropriate Uzbek version of Alexander the Macedonian name "Alexander the Great" for the Uzbek readers this is known as Zulqarnayn in the East. The Qur'an also mentions this historical figure. For example, Surah al-Kahf, verses 302-303 states: "(O Muhammad!) You will be asked about Zulkarnain. Say, "I'll read the news about him to you now." "Indeed, We have given him (Zul-Qarnain) a position in the land and a way to everything." (p. 302-303). The Macedonian (Macedonian) is said to have been born in Macedonia. This means that Uzbek readers can quickly tell who is being talked about. Here Cho'lpon used the exact name of the historical people in the Uzbek language appropriately. It is known from history that Alexander Zulkarnai led his troops to Yaksart (Syrdarya, Uzbekistan) and built the city of Escheta (now Khojand) on its banks. There are a lot of legends about this person in Middle and Central Asia. Almost all Arab

historians have mentioned a great deal about Alexander's conquest of the East in their writings. In particular, Tabari was created in the 9th century, Balaam in the 9th century, Nizami alMulk in the 11th century, Beruni in the X century and others. And in fiction, it can be seen from Firdavsi's "Shohnoma" to Navoi's "Iskandarnoma". Alexander Makedonsky has been interpreted in the Koran by the name of Alexander the Great, as it is stated in the Koran namely Alexander the Great. Exactly this variant has been mentioned by the best translators M. Shaykhzoda and J.Kamol in their translations.

M.Shayxzoda: (Hamlet). - Nima deb o'ylaysan: Iskandar Rumi ham yerda yotganida shu holatda bo'lganmikan? (p150). J.Kamol: O'sha Iskandar Zulqarnayn ham yer ostida shundoq ahvoldamikin? (p 162)

It is noteworthy that these two superstars, unlike Chulpon, bear the ancient name of this great Sardar. This is understandable for Uzbek readers who are familiar with this name, or for older readers. From the second group of nouns, let's have a stop at Feb, Gimenei, Neptune, Tellus.

King:

*Full thirty times hath Phoebus' cart gone round
Neptune's salt wash and Tellus' orb'd ground,
And thirty dozen moons with borrowed sheen
About the world have time twelve thirties been,
Since love, our hearts, and Hymen did our hands,
Unite commutual in most sacred bands. (Page.99.)*

Kanshin:

Вот тридцать раз уже как Феба колесницы-объехала вокруг соленых стран Нептуна – и вокруг округлостей владений твердых Телла-и тридцать дюжен лун уже заёмным-сиянием своим двенадцатьвзаятих раз-мрак тридцат ночей собой разгоняли-с тех пор, как в нас Амур зажер огонь любви, - а Гименей связал нас крепкими цепями. p32).

Cho'ron:

*Ko 'nglimizga sevgilarning olovlarini
Muhabbatning xudovandiy oqqandan beri,
Hech uzulmas ishlar bilan ulug' Himeney
Ikkimizni jipslashtirib qo 'ygandan beri,
Febus tushkan saltanatlik, yengil arava
U Neptunning sho 'r tuproqli keng o 'lkasini
Va "Tella"ning payoni yoq zo 'r mulklarini
O 'ttizda va, o 'ttizda aylanib keldi
O 'n ikki oylardan ham o 'ttizi yana,
O 'z nurini socha-socha o 'n ikkida
O 'ttiz kecha zulmatini yorib tarqatdi! (p368).*

There is some controversy over the fact that Cho'lpon transcribed all of the proper nouns we mentioned above. Several literary critics have blamed Cho'lpon for his actions "for the sake of adequacy." In fact! As we consider the above, we must first focus on that time, the time when Cho'lpon lived and worked.

It is well known that that period was a new era for many Uzbek intelligentsia such as Cho'lpon. It was a real climb. Many intellectuals traveled to different countries (Russia, Turkey, Germany, and other European countries) to pursue their studies. Naturally, this process would also introduce Uzbek readers to new names. Thus, if we look at such a point of view, Cho'lpon could have achieved much success by translating some titles to the Uzbek reader at that time, rather than "failing to achieve". An important part of this is the fact that at the end of the work, comments are made on those new names that played a great role. In the above passage, M. Shaykhzoda only mentions one of the proper nouns - Gimenein. The translator could have gained several achievements in translation. We can say that this is because the names we are learning make sense in translation. For example, he tried to make the reader understand the name Gimeney as "the God of marriage".

Referring to the above-mentioned translators, it should be mentioned, J. Kamol, who is younger and more contemporary than Chulpon and M. Shaykhzoda, the

translator adds the word "God" to the Gimenei, which may seem strange to the Uzbek reader. As we know, most Uzbek readers find the word "divine" only related to "God". When the word "God" is used before Gimeneus, it is necessary to include the word "marriage" to make it clear to the reader. We will have a look at the Hamlet tragedy for the third group of proper nouns. Let's look at how Cholpon, M. Shaykhzoda, and J. Kamals use the name Cain (Cain).

Hamlet: How the knave it to the??? as if 'twere Cain's jawbone, that did the first murder! (Page 148).

П.Канишин: С каким ожесточением выироль его этот олух, словно он челюсть каина, первого убийцы. (стр. 253).

Cho'lpon: Endi kelib ana u tentak, birinchi marta odam o'ldirgan Qobilning chakka suyagiday bo'lib, bor kuchi bilan yerga urayapti. (p113).

Б.Пастернак: А этот негодяй шмыгнул его об земь, то что это челюсть каина, который совершил первое убийство. (p.226)

М.Шайхзода: А бу аблах бо'lsa, го'yo birinchi odam o'ldirgan Qobilning chakka suyagini otayotganiday uni yerga irg'idi. (p 150)

Ж.Камол: Mana bu yaramas esa Qobilni o'ldirib, dunyoda birinchi qotillik qilgan Hobilni jag'ini irg'itganday, buni uloqtirib tashladi. (p 160)

We know that the account of Cain and Abel is quoted in the Koran. Cain and Abel were the descendants of our first human, the first prophet, Adam, and the first woman, Mamo Eve. Verse 27 of Surat al-Ma'ida says, "Tell them the truth about the two sons of Adam (Cain and Abel)! When the two made the sacrifice and the other was not accepted". The above story is said during this Surah: "Then Allah sent a raven out of the ground to show him how to bury his brother's body in it. "Woe to me! Am I too weak to be a raven? I (too) can bury my brother's body. ' Thus, he became one of the regret-bearers. " (Verse, p31) In Christian mythology, they are mentioned as Adam and Eve's children, Cain and Abel. The myth tells us that Cain had a very large land. And Abel was just a shepherd. One day they would bring a gift to God. God did not accept the gift of lazy idle Cain. Because of the anger and

jealousy of his younger brother, Cain killed his brother. In the face of God's wrath, Cain became the first murderer on earth. Cho'lpon and M. Shaykhzoda to some extent; could have succeeded in translating Cain into Uzbek as Cain. Mr. Kamol in this came more from the Islamic viewpoint. He translates Cain as Abel. Cho'lpon lived in Moscow when he translated Hamlet. This certainly had a great impact on translation. The story is that, according to Yunus Maqsudi's book "In the Circle of the Elders," Cho'lpon used to quote the role of Navoi, Fuzuli in the chapters on Islamic history and Quranic verses in the Quran. By noting down Nodirxon the work also underscores that Nodirxon was one of the great scholars of his day. As it turns out, if Hamlet was not translated in Moscow, Cho'lpon could also have come from an Islamic way to translate Cain as Abel. In our view, Cho'lpon probably used the Arabic-Russian dictionary mainly to translate the above name. Avel in Russian is translated as Cain (capable Arab means compromise, silent, obedient), and Cain Abel (Abel means fool, disobedient). However, in the works of QissaiRabguzi (XIV) and Navoi, it is stated that Abel murdered Cain.

As we study the translation of proper nouns in the translations of Cho'lpon, Shaykhzoda, and J.Kamol, let`s have a look at the provision o some ways of translating nouns. There are mainly three ways of translating proper nouns:

A) Transcription; B) Transliteration; C) Direct translation.

Cho'lpon used transcription and transliteration in translating proper nouns, often making comments at the end of the work. Knowing that this method might be a little confusing to the reader, Sheikhzoda gives the translation from its translations. However, Sheikhzoda and J.Kamal often abandon more proper nouns than Cho'lpon. This, of course, was often confusing to the reader. By the way, it is noteworthy that all three have contributed greatly to the study of Shakespeare's legacy through Hamlet. We can only hope that Hamlet will be re-translated in the future, and this will certainly be translated from the original version of the work. Then the mistakes and shortcomings of our translators will be taken into account and the necessary conclusions will be drawn.

REFERENCES:

1. Вежбицкая А. Язык. Культура. Познание. – М.: Русские словари, 1997. – 416 с.
2. Воробьев В.В. Лингвокультурология (Теория и методы). – М., 1997. – 313с.
3. Ермолович Д.И. Имена собственные на стыке языков и культур/ Д.И. Ермолович. – М.: Издат. «Р. Валент», 2001// <http://e-repa.ru/files/translation/ermolovich-names-pt1.pdf>
4. Казакова Т.А. Практические основы перевода / Т.А. Казакова. – СПб.: Союз, 2001. — 320 с.
5. Суперанская А.В. Общая теория имени собственного. – М., 1973. – 372с.
6. Alisherovna, M. B. (2020). Comparative analysis of the English and Russian proverbs and sayings representating the concept" money". Проблемы современной науки и образования, (4-2 (149)), 43-45.
7. qizi Usmonova, U. H., & Mukhtorova, B. (2023). PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF LANGUAGE. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(1), 241-244.
8. Абдуразакова, Ш., & Мухторова, Б. (2023). ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕКСТА. *Scientific progress*, 4(1), 369-373.
9. Mukhtorova, B. (2023). THE LINGUISTIC AND CONCEPTUAL PICTURE OF THE WORLD. *Science and innovation*, 2(B1), 461-466.
10. Мухторова, Б. А. (2022, September). МОДАЛЛИК КАТЕГОРИЯСИНИНГ ЛИСОНИЙ ҲАМДА МАНТИҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 55-61).
11. Makhmudova, N. R. (2019). The use of multimedia learning tools in the English language. *Мировая наука*, (9), 44-48.
12. Abbasova, N. K. (2018). Using Effective Techniques Developing Learners' Critical Thinking in Teaching English Proverbs and Sayings. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (6).

13. Maxmudova, N. (2022). PRAGMATIC SIGNS OF ORNITHONYMS IN PROVERBS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(2), 88-91.
14. Maxmudova, N. (2021). BIRD NAMES REALLY MATTER: FEATURES OF ORNITHONYMES IN LANGUAGE. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 116-118.
15. Maxmudova, N. (2021). LEXICAL-SEMANTIC GROUP OF ORNITHONYMS IN LANGUAGE AND THEIR USE. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(5), 107-116.